

Spiroannulation of a cyclopentane ring. Synthesis of spiro[4.n](n+5)alk-2-en-1-ones[†]

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A methodology based on Claisen rearrangement-Wacker oxidation and intramolecular aldol condensation strategy starting from cyclic ketones leading to spiro[4.n](n+5)alk-2-en-1-ones has been developed. Thus one-pot Claisen rearrangement of the allyl alcohols 6a-c furnished the aldehydes 8a-c, which on regiospecific oxidation using Wacker conditions generated the keto-aldehydes 9a-c. Finally, intramolecular aldol condensation transformed the keto-aldehydes 9a-c into spiroannulated products 10a-c.

Although cyclopentanes have been known in chemical literature for over a century and in Nature from time immemorial, interest in their synthesis and reactions remained on a low key until mid-seventies. Strange as it may seem, this could be traced to the fact that till 1960, relatively few cyclopentanoid natural products of reasonable complexity were known that could constitute challenging targets, and synthetic organic chemists were largely preoccupied and fascinated by the steroidal systems and annulated six-membered rings. However, discoveries and developments in the chemistry of natural and unnatural products have rekindled interest in the synthetic design of cyclopentanoids and a significant amount of activity has been initiated in this area which continues to be a topic of contemporary interest¹. Among the natural products, sesquiterpenes incorporate a variety of complex carbocyclic frameworks. Presence of spiro

fused systems, either simple or as part of a polycyclic carbon framework is commonly encountered in many natural products², e.g. acorones, axisonitrile, chamigrenes, spirovetivanes, lubimin, spirojatamol, angular triquinanes, cedrane, retigeranic acid, ginkgolides, quadrone, junicedranol etc. (Chart 1). The methodology of annulating a functionalised cyclopentane ring onto an existing residue, a cyclopentanulation¹, would have the promise and potential to achieve success if one can control the chemo-, regio- and stereoselectivity of the reactions involved. As a consequence, many methodologies have been developed for this purpose over the last two decades employing novel and innovative strategies, with higher degree of chemo-, regio- and stereochemical control. Comparatively, not much attention was focussed on the development of methods for the annulation of spirofused cyclopentanes.

Chart 1

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri.

For the spiroannulation of a cyclopentane ring, a Claisen rearrangement-Wacker oxidation based methodology was conceived³, which is depicted in Scheme 1 in a retrosynthetic manner. It was anticipated that the spiro fused cyclopentenone **1** could be obtained by the intramolecular aldol condensation of the keto-aldehyde **2** which in turn could be obtained by regiocontrolled oxidation of a 3,3-disubstituted-4-pentalenol **3**. The pentalenol **3**, a γ,δ -unsaturated alcohol, is

the ester **7a** in 94% yield. Regioselective reduction of the ester **7a** at low temperature (-78°) with lithium aluminium hydride in dry ether furnished the allyl alcohol **6a** in 99% yield, whose structure rests secured from its spectral data. For the creation of the quaternary center, necessary for the generation of the spiro system, a one-pot Claisen rearrangement reaction⁴ was employed for the conversion of the allyl alcohol **6a** into the pentalenol **8a**. Thus, thermal activation of

Scheme 1

logically a product of a Claisen rearrangement and the γ,γ -disubstituted allyl alcohol **4** can readily be identified as the appropriate precursor. The allyl alcohol **4** could be obtained from a cyclic ketone via Wittig reaction-regioselective reduction sequence. To test the feasibility of the strategy, the sequence was carried out employing cyclooctanone **5a** as the starting material (Scheme 2).

To begin with, cyclooctanone (**5a**) was converted into the allyl alcohol **6a**, the precursor for the projected Claisen rearrangement, employing a Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction and regioselective reduction protocol. Thus, treatment of the ketone **5a** with sodium salt of triethyl phosphonoacetate in dry THF at room temperature furnished

the allyl alcohol **6a** and ethyl vinyl ether in the presence of a catalytic amount of mercuric acetate at 170° in a sealed tube, furnished the γ,δ -unsaturated aldehyde **8a** in 62% yield, whose structure was established from its IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral data. For the regiospecific conversion of the vinyl group in the pentalenol **8a** into an acetyl group, Wacker oxidation was chosen⁵. Thus, treatment of the pentalenol **8a** with 0.1 equivalent of palladium chloride and 1.0 equivalent of cuprous chloride in dimethylformamide (DMF) and water in the oxygen atmosphere (balloon) for 20 h, furnished the keto-aldehyde **9a** in 80% yield, whose structure was established on the basis of the spectral data. Finally, intramolecular aldol condensation of the keto-aldehyde **9a** with 5%

Scheme 2

methanolic potassium hydroxide in THF at room temperature for 5 h furnished the spiroenone **10a** in 72% yield. Presence of a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 178 (C₁₂H₁₈O) in the mass spectrum and the presence of an IR absorption band at 1700 due to the cyclopentenone carbonyl and at 1600 cm⁻¹ due to the olefinic moiety revealed the formation of the aldol product **10a**. In the ¹H NMR spectrum, presence of two typical triplets of a doublet resonances at δ 7.54 and 6.00 due to the β and α protons, respectively, of a cyclopent-2-enone, a triplet at δ 2.48 due to the γ-methylene, established the structure of the spiroenone **10a**. The ¹³C NMR spectrum with characteristic resonances at δ 215.6 due to the cyclopentenone carbonyl carbon, at 162.1 and 132.3 due to the β and α carbons, respectively, of a cyclopent-2-enone, at 50.3 due to the spiro carbon, at 45.1 due to the γ-methylene carbon and four signals at 32.6 (2C), 28.9 (2C), 25.0 and 23.4 (2C) ppm due to the symmetric seven methylene carbons of the cyclooctane ring confirmed the structure of the spiroenone **10a**.

After successfully demonstrating the applicability of the methodology for the spiro annulation of a cyclopentenone, to establish the generality of the strategy, the sequence was carried out with cyclohexanone **5b** and cyclododecanone **5c** (Scheme 2). Thus, Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction of the ketones **5b,c** with triethyl phosphonoacetate and sodium hydride gave the corresponding α,β-unsaturated esters **7b,c**. Regioselective reduction of the esters **7b,c** with lithium aluminium hydride in dry ether at low temperature (-70°) furnished the allyl alcohols **6b,c**. One-pot Claisen rearrangement of the allyl alcohols **6b,c** using ethyl vinyl ether and a catalytic amount of mercuric acetate in a sealed tube at 170° for 24 h furnished the 3,3-disubstituted pent-4-enals **8b,c**. Conversion of the vinyl group into an acetyl group employing Wacker oxidation process, using 0.1 equivalent of palladium chloride and 1.0 equivalent of cuprous chloride in dimethylformamide and water in the oxygen atmosphere, transformed the pentenals **8b,c** into the keto-aldehydes **9b,c**. Finally, intramolecular aldol condensation of the keto-aldehydes **9b,c** using 1M methanolic KOH in THF at RT furnished the spiroenones **10b,c**.⁶ The structures of all the compounds were established from their spectral data. The methodology has been successfully applied in the total syntheses of the sesquiterpenes tochuinyl acetate and dihydrotochuinyl acetates⁷ and the dihydro-derivatives of the spirojatamol and erythrodiene⁸.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer. ¹H (90 and 300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75

MHz) spectra were recorded on Jeol FX-90Q and JNM λ-300 spectrometers. The chemical shifts (δ ppm) and the coupling constants (Hz) are reported in the standard fashion with reference to either internal tetramethylsilane (for ¹H) or the central line (77.1 ppm) of CDCl₃ (for ¹³C). In the ¹³C NMR spectra, nature of the carbons were identified either by recording off-resonance or DEPT spectra and the multiplicities when recorded are given in parentheses. Mass spectra were recorded using a Jeol JMS-DX 303 GC-MS instrument using a direct inlet mode. Relative intensities of the ions are given in parentheses. Acme's silica gel (100–200 mesh) was used for column chromatography. Dry THF was obtained by distillation over sodium-benzophenone ketyl. Dry ether was obtained by distillation over sodium and stored over sodium wire. DMF was filtered through a neutral alumina column prior to use. Triethyl phosphonoacetate, LiAlH₄, mercuric acetate, PdCl₂ and ethyl vinyl ether were obtained from Fluka and used without further purification.

Ethyl cyclooctylideneacetate (7a) : A suspension of sodium hydride (60% in oil; 500 mg, 13 mmol) in hexanes under nitrogen atmosphere was magnetically stirred for 10 min and the solvent was syringed out. The oil-free sodium hydride was then suspended in dry THF (10 ml) and cooled in an ice-bath. Triethyl phosphonoacetate (3.0 ml, 15 mmol) in dry THF (20 ml) was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. It was then cooled in an ice-bath and a solution of cyclooctanone **5a** (1.26 g, 10 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) was added dropwise and stirred for 8 h at room temperature. It was then quenched by careful addition of saturated aq. NH₄Cl solution and extracted with ether (2 × 15 ml). The combined ether extract was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl-acetate hexane (1 : 19) as eluent furnished the unsaturated ester **7a** (1.85 g, 94%) as an oil : *v*_{max} (neat) 1730, 1650, 890 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 5.72 (1H, s, C=CH), 4.13 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, O-CH₂CH₃), 2.76 (2H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz) and 2.31 (2H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz), 1.80–1.70 (4H, m), 1.50–1.45 (6H, m), 1.27 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, O-CH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 168.4 (C, O-C=O), 166.3 (C, C=CH), 115.5 (CH, C=CH), 59.2 (CH₂, O-CH₂CH₃), 38.7 (CH₂), 30.6 (CH₂), 27.8 (CH₂), 27.6 (CH₂), 26.4 (CH₂), 25.6 (CH₂) and 25.2 (CH₂) [C-2' to 8'], 14.3 (CH₃, O-CH₂CH₃); *m/z* 196 (M⁺, 100%), 168 (45), 151 (65).

2-(Cyclooctylidene)ethanol (6a) : To a cold (-78°), magnetically stirred solution of the unsaturated ester **7a** (1.0 g, 5.1 mmol) in ether (10 ml) was added LAH (97 mg, 2.55

mmol) in one portion. The reaction mixture was stirred at -78° for 2 h and allowed to warm up to -20° over a period of 30 min. Ethyl acetate (2 ml) was carefully introduced to consume the excess reagent and the reaction was quenched with ice-cold water (5 ml). The solution was filtered through a sintered funnel and the residue thoroughly washed with ether (2×20 ml). The ether layer was separated, washed with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was evaporated and the residue was purified on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 10) as eluent to furnish the allyl alcohol **6a** (780 mg, 99%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 3300, 1660, 1020, 990 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.43 (1H, t, J 7.0 Hz, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 4.17 (2H, d, J 7.0 Hz, CH_2OH), 2.23 (2H, t, J 6.0 Hz), 2.19 (2H, t, J 6.0 Hz), 1.70–1.40 (10H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 145.9 (C, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 123.9 (CH, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 59.3 (CH_2 , $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 37.6 (CH_2), 29.0 (CH_2), 28.0 (CH_2), 27.3 (CH_2), 26.1 (CH_2), 25.9 (CH_2), 25.8 (CH_2); m/z 154 (M^+ , 15%), 136 (45), 108 (45), 95 (60), 93 (40), 83 (95).

2-(1-Vinylcyclooctyl)acetaldehyde (8a) : A solution of the allyl alcohol **6a** (550 mg, 3.57 mmol), ethyl vinyl ether (1.54 g, 21.4 mmol) and a catalytic amount of mercuric acetate was heated to 180° for 36 h in a sealed tube under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with ether, washed with aq. NaHCO_3 solution and brine, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 20) as eluent furnished the pentenal **8a** (400 mg, 62%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 1720, 920 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.70 (1H, t, J 3.3 Hz, $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 5.80 (1H, dd, J 17.7 and 11.1 Hz, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.10 (1H, d, J 11.1 Hz) and 5.01 (1H, d, J 17.4 Hz, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.30 (2H, d, J 3.3 Hz, CH_2CHO), 1.80–1.40 (14H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 203.9 (d, $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 145.7 (d, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 113.3 (t, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 52.8 (t, CH_2CHO), 42.2 (s, $\text{C}-1'$), 33.0 (2C), 28.4 (2C), 25.1, 22.3 (2C).

2-(1-Acetylcyclooctyl)acetaldehyde (9a) : A suspension of palladium chloride (11 mg, 0.06 mmol) and cuprous chloride (83 mg, 0.83 mmol) in DMF (0.6 ml) and water (0.42 ml) was magnetically stirred in an oxygen atmosphere, created via evacuative displacement of air using an oxygen balloon, for 1 h at room temperature. A solution of the pentenal **8a** (150 mg, 0.83 mmol) in DMF (0.6 ml) was then added to the reaction mixture and stirred for 20 h at room temperature in the oxygen atmosphere. 2 *N* Aq. HCl was added to the reaction mixture and extracted with ether (2×4 ml). The ether extract was washed with saturated aq. NaHCO_3 solution followed by brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the product

on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the keto aldehyde **9a** (130 mg, 80%) : ν_{max} (neat) 2720, 1720, 1700, 1020 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.63 (1H, s, $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 2.67 (2H, s, H-2), 2.20 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.10–1.90 (2H, m), 1.70–1.50 (12H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 212.6 (C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 200.6 (CH, $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 52.5 (C, $\text{C}-1'$), 51.0 (CH_2 , CH_2CHO), 30.8 (2C, CH_2 C-2' and 8'), 28.3 (2C, CH_2 , C-3' and 7'), 26.4 (CH_3 , COCH_3), 25.3 (CH_2 , C-5'), 23.0 (2C, CH_2 , C-4' and 6').

Spiro[4.7]dodec-2-en-1-one (10a) : To a magnetically stirred solution of the keto aldehyde **9a** (130 mg, 0.66 mmol) in THF (0.4 ml) was added 10% KOH solution (0.8 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred for 8 h at room temperature. Solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. It was then taken in ether (10 ml) and washed with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the spiroenone **10a** (85 mg, 72%) : ν_{max} (neat) 1700, 1590, 950 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (90 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.54 (1H, t of d, J 5.6 and 2.7 Hz, H-3), 6.00 (1H, t of d, J 5.6 and 2.2 Hz, H-2), 2.48 (2H, t, J 2.5 Hz, H-4), 2.00–1.20 (14H, m, H-6 to 12); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 215.6 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 162.1 (C-3), 132.3 (C-2), 50.3 (C-5), 45.1 (C-4), 32.6 (2C, C-6 and 12), 28.9 (2C, C-7 and 11), 25.0 (C-9), 23.4 (2C, C-8 and 10); m/z 178 (M^+ , 20%), 149 (15), 121 (24), 108 (20), 107 (26), 95 (100), 82 (42).

Ethyl cyclohexylideneacetate (7b) : Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction of cyclohexanone (**5b**; 1.0 g, 10.2 mmol) using sodium hydride (60% in oil, 460 mg, 12 mmol) and triethyl phosphonoacetate (3.0 ml, 15 mmol) in dry THF (8 ml) for 8 h as described for compound **7a**, and purification of the product over a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 40) as eluent furnished the unsaturated ester **7b** (1.6 g, 94%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 1720, 1660, 860 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.47 (1H, br s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 4.06 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.78 (2H, t), 2.15 (2H, t), 1.58 (6H, br s), 1.23 (3H, t, J 6.8 Hz, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 166.2 (C, $\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 162.8 (C, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 113.2 (CH, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 59.2 (CH_2 , $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 38.0 (CH_2), 29.7 (CH_2), 28.7 (CH_2), 27.8 (CH_2), 26.4 (CH_2), 14.4 (CH_3 , $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

2-Cyclohexylideneethanol (6b) : Regioselective reduction of the unsaturated ester **7b** (1.6 g, 9.52 mmol) in dry ether (20 ml) using LAH (180 mg, 4.76 mmol) for 2 h as described for compound **6a**, and purification of the product over a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 20 to 1 : 10) as eluent furnished the allyl alcohol **6b** (1.1 g,

92%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 3300, 1670 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.32 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 4.08 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 2.20–2.00 (4H, m), 1.50 (6H, br s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 144.1 (C, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 120.2 (CH, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 58.3 (CH_2 , $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 36.9 (CH_2), 28.7 (CH_2), 28.3 (CH_2), 27.7 (CH_2), 26.6 (CH_2); m/z 126 (M^+ , 15%), 109 (100), 108 (80), 93 (40).

2-(1-Vinylcyclohexyl)acetaldehyde (8b) : One-pot Claisen rearrangement of the allyl alcohol **6b** (270 mg, 2.14 mmol) with ethyl vinyl ether (848 mg, 11.8 mmol) and a catalytic amount of mercuric acetate at 170° for 36 h and work-up as described for the aldehyde **8a** followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 20) as eluent furnished the pentenal **8b** (220 mg, 68%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 2720, 1720, 920 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.70 (1H, t, J 3.3 Hz, $\text{H-C}=\text{O}$), 5.80 (1H, dd, J 18.0 and 11.1 Hz, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.18 (1H, dd, J 11.1 and 1.1 Hz) and 5.07 (1H, dd, J 18.0 and 1.1 Hz, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.30 (2H, d, J 3.3 Hz, CH_2CHO), 1.70–1.40 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{CCl}_4$) δ 203.7 (CH, $\text{H-C}=\text{O}$), 144.7 (CH, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 114.1 (CH_2 , $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 53.3 (CH_2 , CH_2CHO), 39.1 (C, C-1'), 36.0 (2C, CH_2 , C-2' and 6'), 25.9 (CH_2 , C-4'), 21.7 (2C, CH_2 , C-3' and 5'); m/z 152 (M^+ , 15%), 125 (25), 109 (100), 81 (50), 73 (100).

2-(1-Acetylcyclohexyl)acetaldehyde (9b) : Wacker oxidation of the vinyl group in the aldehyde **8b** (200 mg, 1.32 mmol) with palladium chloride (17.5 mg, 0.1 mmol) and cuprous chloride (132 mg, 1.33 mmol) in DMF (1.0 ml) and water (0.5 ml) in an oxygen atmosphere for 20 h and work-up as described for the keto aldehyde **9a** followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 50 to 1 : 20) as eluent furnished the keto aldehyde **9b** (75 mg, 79%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1720, 1700 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.66 (1H, t, J 1.8 Hz, $\text{H-C}=\text{O}$), 2.69 (2H, d, J 1.8 Hz, CH_2CHO), 2.20 (3H, s, COCH_3), 1.85–1.75 (2H, m), 1.60–1.40 (8H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 212.5 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 200.9 ($\text{H-C}=\text{O}$), 50.3 (C-1'), 48.5 (CH_2CHO), 32.7 (2C, C-2' and 6'), 25.5 (C-4'), 25.4 (COCH_3), 21.9 (2C, C-3' and 5').

Spiro[4.5]dec-2-en-1-one (10b) : Intramolecular aldol condensation of the keto aldehyde **9b** (75 mg, 0.45 mmol) in THF (0.25 ml) with 1M methanolic KOH solution (0.6 ml) for 8 h at room temperature and work-up as described for the spiroenone **10a**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 49 to 1 : 20) as eluent furnished the spiroenone **10b**⁶ (50 mg, 75%) : ν_{\max} (neat) 1690, 1590 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (90 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.57 (1H, t of d, J 5.6 and 2.7 Hz, H-3),

6.07 (1H, t of d, J 5.7 and 2.2 Hz, H-2), 2.50 (2H, t, J 2.5 Hz, H-4), 2.00–1.10 (10H, m, H-6 to 10); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 214.7 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 162.2 (C-3), 132.3 (C-2), 47.9 (C-5), 42.0 (C-4), 33.2 (2C, C-6 and 10), 25.2 (C-8), 23.0 (2C, C-7 and 9); m/z 150 (M^+ , 25%), 108 (26), 95 (100), 82 (40).

Ethyl cyclododecylideneacetate (7c) : Wittig-Horner-Emmons reaction of cyclododecanone (**5c**, 2.0 g, 11 mmol) using sodium hydride (60% in oil, 536 mg, 14 mmol) and triethyl phosphonoacetate (3.2 ml, 16 mmol) in dry THF (30 ml) for 8 h at room temperature and work-up as described for the ester **7a**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate and hexane (1 : 19) as eluent furnished the unsaturated ester **7c** (2.65 g, 96%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1720, 1640, 870 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.75 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 4.14 (2H, q, J 7.0 Hz, $\text{O-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.72 (2H, t, J 6.6 Hz), 2.21 (2H, t, J 6.6 Hz), 1.70–1.20 (21H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 166.9 (C, $\text{O-C}=\text{O}$), 163.0 (C, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 116.2 (CH, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 59.4 (CH_2 , OCH_2CH_3), 32.8 (CH_2), 29.8 (CH_2), 25.0 (CH_2), 24.9 (CH_2), 24.1 (CH_2), 2.0 (2C, CH_2), 23.7 (CH_2), 23.4 (CH_2), 22.9 (CH_2), 22.1 (CH_2), 14.3 (CH_3 , OCH_2CH_3); m/z 252 (M^+ , 25%), 207 (55), 164 (60), 128 (100), 95 (50).

2-Cyclododecylideneethanol (6c) : Regioselective reduction of the unsaturated ester **7c** (1.0 g, 3.96 mmol) in dry ether (10 ml) with LAH (76 mg, 2.0 mmol) at -78° to -20° for 30 min and work-up as described for the alcohol **6a**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 10) as eluent furnished the allyl alcohol **6c** (820 mg, 99%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 3300 (O-H), 1650, 710 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.50 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 4.18 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 2.13–2.06 (4H, m), 1.70–1.20 (18H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 142.1 (C, C-1'), 124.0 (CH, C-2), 59.3 (CH_2 , $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 31.5 (CH_2), 28.9 (CH_2), 25.0 (CH_2), 24.9 (CH_2), 24.1 (CH_2), 24.0 (CH_2), 23.9 (CH_2), 23.8 (CH_2), 23.2 (CH_2), 23.0 (CH_2), 22.1 (CH_2); m/z 210 (M^+ , 12%), 192 (22), 109 (45), 97 (60), 96 (55), 95 (75).

2-(1-Vinylcyclododecyl)acetaldehyde (8c) : One-pot Claisen rearrangement of the allyl alcohol **6c** (600 mg, 2.85 mmol) with ethyl vinyl ether (1.02 g, 14.2 mmol, 1.4 ml) and a catalytic amount of mercuric acetate at 180° for 36 h and work-up as described for the aldehyde **8a**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 20) as eluent furnished the aldehyde **8c** (420 mg, 63%) as an oil : ν_{\max} (neat) 1720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.65 (1H, t, J 3.3 Hz, $\text{H-C}=\text{O}$), 5.84

(1H, dd, J 18.0 and 10.8 Hz, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.09 (1H, d, J 11.1 Hz), 5.00 (1H, d, J 17.7 Hz, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.27 (2H, d, J 3.3 Hz, CH_2CHO), 1.50–1.20 (22H, m, H-2' to 12').

2-(1-Acetylcyclododecyl)acetaldehyde (9c) : Wacker oxidation of the vinyl group in the aldehyde **8c** (250 mg, 1.05 mmol) with palladium chloride (14.1 mg, 0.08 mmol) and cuprous chloride (105 mg, 1.06 mmol) in DMF (1.0 ml) and water (0.6 ml) in an oxygen atmosphere for 20 h at RT and work-up as described for the keto aldehyde **9a**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent furnished the keto aldehyde **9c** (200 mg, 76%) as an oil : ν_{max} (neat) 1720, 1700 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (90 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.60 (1H, br s, $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 2.70 (2H, br s, H-2), 2.20 (3H, s, COCH_3), 1.70–1.20 (22H, m, ring methylenes).

Spiro[4.11]hexadec-2-en-1-one (10c) : Intramolecular aldol condensation of the keto aldehyde **9c** (55 mg, 0.22 mmol) in THF (2 ml) with 1M methanolic KOH solution (2 drops) at RT for 8 h and work-up as described for the spiroenone **10a**, followed by purification of the product on a silica gel column using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 20 to 1 : 9) as eluent furnished the enone **10c** (35 mg, 66%) : ν_{max} (neat) 1690, 1580, 810 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.55 (1H, t of d, J 5.7 and 2.7 Hz, H-3), 6.05 (1H, t of d, J 6.0 and 2.4 Hz, H-2), 2.45 (2H, t, J 2.5 Hz, H-4), 1.50–1.30 (22H, m, H-6 to 16); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 214.3 (C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 161.2 (CH, C-3), 132.2 (CH, C-2), 49.3 (C, C-5), 43.7 (CH_2 , C-4), 30.9 (2C, CH_2), 26.6 (2C, CH_2), 26.0 (CH_2), 22.7 (2C, CH_2), 22.2 (2C, CH_2), 19.5 (2C, CH_2); m/z 234 (M^+ , 16%), 121 (10), 108 (15), 107 (16), 95 (100), 82 (35).

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